

A Methodological Approach for Multi-Service DS-TE Network Performance Evaluation under Bandwidth Allocation Methods and Path Selection Constraints

Walter da C. P. Neto¹, Rafael F. Reale^{1,2}, Joberto S. B. Martins¹

¹Salvador University (UNIFACS)

²Instituto Federal da Bahia (IFBA)

wcpneto@gmail.com, reale@ifba.edu.br, joberto@unifacs.br

Abstract: Path selection and bandwidth management have a number of different routing protocols (CSPF, OSPF, other), bandwidth allocation models (BAMs) and overall implementation approaches like RDM (Russian Doll Model) [1], Adapt-RDM [6], GRDM (Generalized Russian Dolls Model) [8] and AllocTC-sharing [7] that can be used in the context of a multiservice DS-TE (DiffServ Aware - MPLS Traffic Engineering) network. This paper initially identifies the path selection and bandwidth allocation model (BAM) solutions currently used. Subsequently, it proposes a generic performance evaluation methodology in order to deal with the modeling and implementation scenarios resulting from different routing protocols and BAM options available. The focus adopted is, fundamentally, to provide managers with a methodological approach consisting of a set of steps that can be used to deal with the issues such as network configuration and performance evaluation in the context of multi-service DS-TE networks under BAM constraints. It is expected that the proposed methodological approach could reduce the inherent difficulties found by managers in dealing with BAM model application in multi-service DS-TE networks.

Keywords: DS-TE, Bandwidth Allocation Model, Path Selection Algorithm, Performance Evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-service networks attempt to support a huge variety of multimedia application and services (Voice-over-IP, distributed games, video on demand, IPTV, others) involving data, voice, and video traffic with different characteristics, service level agreements (SLAs) and priorities. Potentially, multi-service networks may bring important advantages for network managers and implementers such as the possibility of traffic integration, bandwidth optimization, reduction of operational cost and OAM (operation, administration and management) integration, among other possibilities.

Multi-service network design, operation and management also present some significant challenges. One of these challenges consists in dynamically allocate usually scarce and limited network resources such as link capacity among a distinct set of applications with diverse Service Level Agreements (SLA).

Solutions for this issue must effectively consider applications grouping in order to deal with scalability, the quality of service implementation in routers for these groups of applications and their traffic engineering and distribution over network links considering the available resources and constraints.

The IETF has proposed the requirements to support MPLS Traffic Engineering-aware DiffServ Services (DS-TE) and, in general, its target is, mainly, to bring together the inherent advantages of both MPLS-TE and DiffServ technologies [2]. In effect, DS-TE proposal corresponds to a flexible and efficient architecture where per-class traffic engineering is adopted by mapping the traffic of a given DiffServ class on specific LSPs created (setup) with MPLS-TE support.

DS-TE [2] introduces the concept of Traffic Class (TC) which will, in practice, accommodate the variety of multimedia and data applications existing in a multi-service network. In addition, DS-TE is an architecture allowing the implementation of Traffic Engineering (TE) for traffic classes (TC). In this scenario each TC will accommodate various and distinct LSPs (MPLS Label Switched Paths) belonging to the supported users and services (VoIP, video, streaming, others).

DS-TE supports 08 different Traffic Classes (TCs) (TC0-TC7) and a TC may accommodate any set of applications and services defined by network administration, management, traffic engineering computation or DiffServ implementation [6]. In DS-TE, by convention, TC0 is the class supporting best effort traffic (lower priority) and TC7 hosts the higher priority traffic. Obviously, each TC may accommodate a number of applications (services) with various LSPs which, in turn, transport application's traffic.

In DS-TE it's necessary to adopt a Bandwidth Allocation (constraint) Model (BAM) or, alternatively, a Bandwidth Constraint model (BC) [2][3]. They, fundamentally, define the limits and rules adopted for link utilization by different class types.

There are two main goals associated with DS-TE networks [2] in relation to BAMs:

1. Try to select an available path using a path selection algorithm for each new LSP request arrival; and
2. Manage the LSPs that are already established in order to keep the BCs rules with a new LSP establishment.

The first goal corresponds to verify TC bandwidth availability for all links in the path. The second goal corresponds to verify the need or not of LSPs "preemption" (effectively, bandwidth preemption) in relation to other priority TCs.

This paper presents the most important aspects of a generic methodology in order to model step-by-step the main goals of a DS-TE network design using DS-TE technology with BAM constraints. It is expected that the proposed methodology will provide to developers a less complex set of steps in order to evaluate the performance in DS-TE networks. It is also expected that the methodology will provide some insight for manager's tasks such as network link configuration and multi-service application's map in classes (priority class). Another expected goal of the proposed methodology is to facilitate new developments for path selection algorithms and BAM models in DS-TE networks. The methodology initially introduced by describing the steps involved with the LSP setup in DS-TE networks with a BAM model. Following that, the methodology is illustrated with a set of simulations in specific scenarios considering two bandwidth allocation implementation models [5] [6] [7].

The paper is organized as follows: section 2 introduces DS-TE concepts and related bandwidth allocation models (BAM); section 3 presents step-by-step the proposed methodology identifying and highlighting its main characteristics. In section 4 a DS-TE network is simulated in order to illustrate the application and validate (proof of concept) the proposed methodology and, finally, concluding remarks are presented in section 5.

II. DS-TE NETWORKS AND BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION MODEL (BAM)

A. DS-TE ARCHITECTURE

DS-TE makes MPLS aware of Traffic Class (TC). TC definition, in practice, organizes and defines priorities for a variety of multimedia applications existing in a multi-service network. DS-TE defines 08 different Traffic Classes (TCs) (TC0-TC7) and a TC may accommodate any set of applications and services defined by network administration, management, traffic engineering computation or DiffServ implementation.

In DS-TE, by convention, TC0 is the class supporting best effort traffic (lower priority) and TC7 hosts the higher priority traffic. Obviously, each TC may accommodate a number of applications (services) mapped on any number of label switched paths (LSPs) transporting application's traffic.

B. BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION MODELS AND LABEL SWITCHED PATH (LSP) SETUP

The Bandwidth Allocation Models (BAMs), in brief, define the amount and sharing of bandwidth available for Traffic Classes (TCs) for a given link. TCs accommodate different types of applications which dynamically generate LSPs setup requests. In this context, the BAM adopted determines whether the new requested LSP setup will be granted, blocked or eventually trigger a preemption process involving other LSPs for a given link.

Bandwidth allocation models, when adopted, are part of the LSP end-to-end path setup and path computation is achieved in close relation and interactively with the adopted BAM.

In effect, BAMs determine LSP setup grant, blocking or preemption need for each individual link separately. This process has to be repeated systematically and interactively for all links in the computed LSP path from origin to destination. As such, bandwidth allocation models do interact with LSP path computation software like CSPF -Constrained Shortest Path First [9], BGP – Border Gateway Protocol or any other in order to achieve an end-to-end LSP path computation. Subsequently to this step and once LSP end-to-end path is fully calculated, a signaling protocol like RSVP-TE – Resource Reservation Protocol for Traffic Engineering, LDP-CR – Constraint-Based Label Distribution Protocol or any other should be invoked for actual LSP setup.

C. BANDWIDTH ALLOCATION MODELS – IETF STANDARDS AND OTHER CONTRIBUTIONS

The MAM (Maximum Allocation Bandwidth Model) model standardized by IETF [3] defines a maximum percentage of link bandwidth utilization for each TC belonging to the link. The summation of individual TCs bandwidth allocation may not exceed the total link bandwidth available and no sharing among TCs is possible. This BAM model is not the most efficient strategy in terms of network resources utilization.

The Russian Doll Model (RDM) [1] standardized by IETF proposes the sharing of unused bandwidth among TCs. In RDM, by convention, TCs with higher values are hierarchically superior to TCs with lower values (Fig. 01) and the Bandwidth Allocation Model behaves as follows:

- All LSPs associated with TC2 do not use a bandwidth greater than BC2 (BC – Bandwidth Constraint);
- All LSPs associated with TC1 and TC2 do not use bandwidth greater than BC1;
- All LSPs associated with TC0, TC1 and TC2 do not use bandwidth greater than BC0.

Figure 1. Russian Dolls Model (RDM)

The RDM Model allows the sharing of bandwidth (BCs) among traffic classes (TCs). Preemption is used to achieve isolation among TCs [1].

In RDM, the free bandwidth of higher priority classes can be temporarily used by lower priority classes. In this scenario, priority LSP setup considers the "preemption" of low priority LSPs/classes whenever necessary. A practical implementation and a performance evaluation of IETF RDM is present in [5][6] focused on an effective preemption strategy in RDM context.

The Generalized-RDM (G-RDM) [8] model has the intention to explore at the same time the best characteristics of MAM and RDM models. The links are virtually separated in two

different bandwidth chunks. In the first one, link capacity is shared according with the RDM model (sharing the bandwidth among TCs) and, in the second one, the link capacity is shared according with the MAM model (isolating the TC bandwidth).

Another BAM is the AllocTC-Sharing [7] in which the bandwidth is fully shared among different TCs in an opportunistic style. The AllocTC-Sharing model adopts two different styles for bandwidth sharing concomitantly (Fig. 2):

- The “high-to-low” (HTL) bandwidth allocation; and
- The “low-to-high” (LTH) bandwidth allocation.

The “high-to-low” (HTL) bandwidth allocation style is the classical alternative used in RDM model. In this case, the non-used bandwidth reserved for high priority classes may be temporarily allocated to low priority classes (Fig. 2).

The “low-to-high” (LTH) bandwidth allocation style innovates by allowing high priority classes temporarily allocate non-used bandwidth primarily reserved for low priority classes. In this particular alternative the amount of bandwidth taken from low priority classes is named “loan” (Fig. 2).

In both styles LSP preemption is used to preserve the defined bandwidth constraint (BCs) for the traffic classes.

Fundamentally, AllocTC-Sharing preserves the bandwidth constraints (BCs) defined by network managers for all classes and, beyond that, allows an opportunistic use of non-used bandwidth on the link.

Figure 2. AllocTC-Sharing “High-to-Low” and “Low-to-High” Bandwidth Allocation Alternatives

CSPF (Constraint Shortest Path First) is a commonly adopted routing protocol that has been extended by RFC 4124 [2] for path computation considering Traffic Classes (TCs) in DS-TE networks. In effect, CSPF-aware DS-TE extension considers the bandwidth available on a per-class (TC) basis instead of aggregate link bandwidth. As such, the bandwidth allocation model (BAM) adopted ultimately defines the “per-

link” bandwidth availability and directly influences CSPF performance characteristics such as LSP grant, preemption and blocking.

Considering the inherent operation of BAMs, it is very important to evaluate the integration of bandwidth allocation models (BAMs) with path selection algorithms, like, for instance, CSPF. BAMs and path computation protocol integration have a number of possible combinations and, as such, an evaluation approach is required in order to deal with the variability of alternatives and facilitate network configuration by managers.

III. A METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR DS-TE NETWORKS PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. DS-TE NETWORK GENERAL DATA STRUCTURE AND SYSTEM DEFINITIONS

The methodological approach proposed is based on a centralized management operation, in a bandwidth broker style, in which a management entity (Fig. 3) has the knowledge about the established LSPs; the traffic classes (TCs) and the bandwidth constraints (BCs) defined on the network (Table I).

Figure 3. Centralized DS-TE management

TABLE I
MANAGEMENT ENTITY VARIABLES

Variable	Description
A_BC[n]	Array with the actual bandwidth constraints used for each link in the network ($0 \leq n \leq \text{Max TCs available}$)
MAX_BC[n]	Array with the maximum bandwidth constraints allowed for each link in the network ($0 \leq n \leq \text{Max TCs available}$)
New_LSP_Band	Bandwidth of a new LSP requisition
Max_Paths_Available	Maximum paths number available among different OD nodes for a new LSP requisition

Whenever a new LSP setup request associated to one CT arrives in the network, the manager entity will evaluate if the available residual capacity in the corresponding BC is sufficient for all links belonging to the LSP path. For the proposed approach, the “bandwidth manager entity database” has stored for all links the established LSPs grouped per TC (Fig. 4).

The LSPs are ordered accordingly with a specific parameter or combinations of parameters (LSP queuing factor) that is determined by the network designer. In case of preemption is needed the last LSP is select. LSPs that are associated with

more than one link must be stored for all links in the path.

Figure 4. LSPs grouped by TC in the database

In the manager entity, each two different Origin-Destination traffic flows have an associated path matrix with all the possible paths among different nodes. The paths (lines) are represented by letters and the links (columns) are represented by numbers (Table II):

TABLE II
PATH INFORMATION STORED - MANAGER ENTITY

Path	Links			
1	B	C	-	-
2	A	E	F	-
3	B	C	G	H

B. DS-TE NETWORK MODELING AND SIMULATION APPROACH

In the methodological approach proposed, DS-TE network operation is represented by the “execution cycle” of a group of events ordered in a list (event chain) in chronological order. The event chain processing (removal and insertion of the events associated with the DS-TE network system) is based on the SMPL philosophy [10] as follows:

Figure 5. DS-TE Network Event Chain Approach

The DS-TE operation modeling considering the BAM alternatives and a path selection protocol (CSPF or another) alternatives has events and modules as shown in Figure 6.

The “event machine” treats or triggers three different event types.

Figure 6. DS-TE Operation Modeling - Events, Modules and Main Steps

Event 1: LSP setup request(new LSP generation)

This event treated by the event machine generates a LSPs setup request (Origin-Destination) associate with its specific TC and network nodes. The LSP setup requests are generated using an exponential distribution arrival time (typical) or any other distribution. The following definitions are necessary for event 1 processing:

- Origin-Destination nodes.
- LSP bandwidth: It is based in the uniform distribution (or another one), with minimal and maximal bandwidth values specified for each different TC existing in the network.
- LSP queuing factor: It is the LSPs preemption criteria for its TC. The queuing factor is necessary to preempt LSPs that might be using the actual non-utilized bandwidth of other TCs or LSPs.

Event 2: LSP establishment attempt (LSP setup)

LSP setup is attempted in this event. Three main execution modules are associated with this event.

The **path selection module** is responsible to calculate the “best path” using the criteria adopted by the path selection algorithm (protocol). In case there is at least one possible path available, it is determined according with the application characteristics and/or a statistical distribution the LSP life time (time it will be kept active). This parameter corresponds to the actual time LSPs will be active as required by the applications and services using it. Various alternative multiservice configuration scenarios (different sets of applications and services) can be effectively simulated by adjusting the “LSP life time” parameter.

If there is no path that meets the LSP and BAM constraints, the LSP will be blocked. The main path selection parameters used by the module are shown below:

- Network Path Matrix: Identifies the possible paths between different Origin-Destination nodes.
- Path Selection Algorithm identifier: Identifies in the data structure the path selection algorithm (protocol) that might be used to calculate the path among the options available.
- The maximum limit of BC value that can be used for the new LSP request. This BC has the same number identification of the TC to which the new LSP request belongs.

In general terms, the **preemption module** is responsible to verify LSPs preemption need in order to free the bandwidth necessary to accommodate the new LSP being established. The verification is done considering the path that was computed by the **path selection module**, so that no set of BCs in the path have exceeded their maximum values. The bandwidth allocation models define the way the available bandwidth is shared among TCs and, as such, define the precise way this module is effectively implemented. The main parameters of the **preemption module** are:

- The Bandwidth Allocation Model (BAM) adopted and its configuration parameters.
- The computed path (Origin to Destination set of links).
- The BC's maximum limit and a vector with the actual BC value (actual BC bandwidth occupation) associated with the LSPs in the TC corresponding to the new LSP request for all links in the path.

The **resource allocation module** is responsible for the establishment of the new requested LSP (*LSP setup*). This module, in actual DS-TE networks, should invoke any signaling protocol like RSVP-TE or LDP-CR for LSP setup. In terms of the methodological approach to evaluate the performance of the DS-TE network, this module updates the network configuration parameters and statistics at the management entity in order to represent the new set of LSPs established. Configuration parameters and other operational data updated for all links in the path include:

- New LSP configuration data (configuration database);
- Actual link bandwidth occupation; and
- Actual BC's bandwidth occupation.

Event 3: LSP teardown (deactivation)

The event 3 corresponds to LSP teardown (deactivation). LSP teardown occurs in two different ways:

- LSP shut down by the application or service using it; or
- By preemption due to TCs bandwidth competition (lack of bandwidth for all application and services).

In terms of the methodological approach used the LSP shutdown is equivalent to LSP "life time" (establishment time) expiration. The management entity is reported in order to represent the LSP teardown as follows:

- LSP removal of the data structure (database) (for all links in the path and TC group);
- Update the actual link bandwidth occupation; and
- Update the actual BC's bandwidth occupation.

IV. DS-TE PERFORMANCE EVALUATION PARAMETERS

A minimum set of evaluation parameters for the DS-TE network is presented in this section. The main focus considered are, firstly, the parameters related with the LSP dynamicity and,

secondly, the Bandwidth Allocation Model impact on network utilization in terms of links and user requirements (BC configuration).

A. DS-TE CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS

The DS-TE basic configuration parameters are as follows:

- Number of Traffic Classes (TCs);
- Bandwidth Constraint (BC's) - maximum value;
- DS-TE network topology and capacity (link's bandwidth);
- Traffic Origin-Destination (OD);
- Path selection criteria;
- LSP preemption criteria; and
- LSP setup request generation.

The number of TCs is a network manager choice and multi-service applications are mapped onto the defined TCs. The Traffic OD is associated with each possible LSP communication between two nodes (source node and destination node). The path selection criteria corresponds to the metric used by the path selections algorithm or protocol and includes number of hops and minimum number of preemptions, among others. The LSP preemption criteria define the parameter used (priority, bandwidth released, other) to opt for LSPs preemption when required by the BAM model adopted. The LSP setup request generation parameter follows the application's traffic profile (multi-service network) by modeling the LSPs setup request arrival time, establishment time and bandwidth usage.

B. DS-TE PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS – LSP AND BAM BEHAVIOR

The following evaluation parameters minimally indicate the DS-TE network behavior in terms of LSP dynamicity and its relation with the BAM parameters configuration impact (BCs and TCs definitions and usage).

- Network's link utilization;
- TCs bandwidth utilization;
- Number and relation between active LSPs, preempted LSPs and blocked LSPs;
- LSP setup up average time for TCs; and
- LSP's inter arrival average time for TCs.

The first parameter reflects the actual network usage and overall efficiency. The BAM control parameters behavior (BCs and TCs) indicate the actual behavior of the adopted BAM model. Finally, the LSP dynamicity parameters (LSPs active, preempted and blocked) reflect the behavior of the multi-service applications supported by the network.

C. OTHER GENERAL EVALUATION ASPECTS TO BE CONSIDERED BY THE NETWORK DESIGNER AND/OR MANAGER

There are some systemic aspects of the multi-service DS-TE network that can be explored by the network designer or manager.

- BAM's influence:
 - The impact of different bandwidth allocation models (BAMs) on the DS-TE performance parameters can be evaluated.
- Protocol's influence:
 - Different path selection algorithms (protocols) can be evaluated in relation to DS-TE performance parameters.
- Traffic Matrix Profile's influence (multi-service characteristics of the network):
 - The variation of LSP's setup request inter arrival average time corresponds to actual traffic matrix profile of the network and, as such, allows the evaluation of link (bandwidth) utilization and other DS-TE performance parameters for a multi-service scenario.
- BC's influence:
 - The BC configuration parameter can be evaluated in terms of finding the one that optimizes bandwidth utilization and reduces LSPs preemption for the traffic pattern adopted. It is important to highlight that BC definition is one of the most challenging aspects of network design in a multi-service scenario.

V. CASE STUDY AND PROOF OF CONCEPT

In this section a case study is presented as a proof-of-concept for the proposed methodological approach for DS-TE network performance evaluation.

The case study developed uses the AllocTC-Sharing bandwidth allocation model and the BAMSIm (Bandwidth Allocation Model Simulator) simulator [7] [5].

The system parameters and scenarios adopted are as follows:
 - The simulated topology (Fig. 7.) uses 03 traffic sources (S1, S2, S3) with 02 sources of interference traffic and one destination (D):

Figure 7. Proof-of-Concept – Simulated Topology

- LSP setup request arrival interval is modeled exponentially as follows (“S1”):

- LSPs – TC₀ – 1 s
- LSPs – TC₁ – 2 s
- LSPs – TC₂ – 4 s

- “S₂” and “S₃” interference traffic are modeled exponentially as follows:

- LSPs – TC₀ – 20 s
- LSPs – TC₁ – 22 s
- LSPs – TC₂ – 24 s

- Number of LSPs: 1.000

- Evenly distributed LSP bandwidth: 05 Mbps to 20 Mbps

- Exponentially modeled LSP time life: average of 150 seconds (should cause link saturation)

- Simulation stops criteria: number of LSPs requested

- Links: 622 Mbps (STM-4 – SDH)

- Traffic Classes (TCs): TC₀, TC₁ and TC₂

- Bandwidth Constraints (BCs) according to Table III.

TABLE III
BANDWIDTH CONSTRAINT (BCS) PER TRAFFIC CLASS (TCs)

BC	Max BC (%)	MAX BC (Mbps)	TC per BC
BC ₀	100	622	TC ₀ +TC ₁ +TC ₂
BC ₁	70	435,4	TC ₁ +TC ₂
BC ₂	40	248,8	TC ₂

- CSPF [9] algorithm is defined for path selection using minimum number of hops for path definition.

- The preemption criteria adopted is “lower priority” for LSPs in each TC.

Some basic DS-TE performance evaluation parameters are illustrated next.

Network's link utilization and link load by TCs are showed in figures 8 and 9. It is perceived that the network link utilization reaches the top (600 Mbps) very soon and that, gradually, LSPs setup requests from other TCs distributes the traffic among the traffic classes involved. This is the effective characteristics of the AllocTC-Sharing model. The TC traffic has to be adapted always to comply with the configured BCs (BC₀=100, BC₁=70 and BC₂=40). When there is a resource competition among different TCs, independently of the BAM adopted, the behavior has to converge to the BCs values configured.

Figure 8. Link utilization

Figure 11. LSP blocking by Traffic Class (TCs)

Figure 9. TC's load

VI. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In DS-TE networks, bandwidth management and path definitions are fundamental aspects of network's efficacy and operation that impact, among other aspects, the bandwidth sharing, the efficient usage of network resources and traffic isolation among different TCs. This paper presented a methodological approach in order to guide new implementations and performance evaluation of DS-TE networks using multiple Bandwidth Allocation Models (BAMs) and path selection algorithms currently available. We argue that the methodological approach presented may facilitate DS-TE network projects and its systematic evaluation in different traffic scenarios.

An important impact of the bandwidth allocation models is the number of preemptions resulting from model's characteristics. Figure 10 shows the number of LSPs preempted associated with the high priority TC TC2. The preemptions occur after the arrival of competing traffic with the LSPs setup requests for TC₀ and TC₁.

Figure 11 illustrates LSPs blocking by traffic class. It is perceived that AllocTC-Sharing blocks LSP requests only after the link becomes saturated and no bandwidth is effectively available, which, in effect corresponds to its main advantage and characteristics.

VII. REFERENCES

Figure 10. LSPs Preemption by Traffic Class (TCs)

- [1] F. Le Faucheur, "Russian dolls bandwidth constraints model for DiffServ-aware MPLS traffic engineering", IETF, RFC 4127, June 2005.
- [2] F. Le Faucheur and W. Lai, "Requirements for support of differentiated services-aware MPLS traffic engineering", IETF, RFC 3564, July 2003.
- [3] W. Lai, "Bandwidth constraints models for Diffserv-aware MPLS traffic engineering: performance evaluation", IETF, RFC 4128, June 2005.
- [4] F. Le Faucheur and W. Lai, "Maximum allocation bandwidth constraints model for DiffServ-aware MPLS traffic engineering", IETF, RFC 4125, June 2005.
- [5] W. Pinto Neto and J. Martins, "A RDM-like Bandwidth Management Algorithm for Traffic Engineering with DiffServ and MPLS Support", Proceedings da 15th International Conference on Telecommunications - ICT, St. Peterburg, Rússia, 2008.
- [6] W. Pinto Neto, J. Martins e S. Brito, "Algoritmos de Seleção de Caminho e Gerenciamento de Banda Compartilhada conforme ao Modelo RDM para Classes de Tráfego em Rede DS-TE", 26º Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos, SBRC, Rio de Janeiro - RJ, 2008.
- [7] R. Reale, J. Martins and W. Pinto Neto, "Modelo de Alocação de Banda com Compartilhamento Oportunista entre Classes de Tráfego e Aplicações em Redes Multiserviço", Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos SBRC, Campo Grande - MS, 2011.
- [8] D. Adami, C. Callegari, S. Giordano M. Pagano and M. Toninelli, "G-RDM: a New Bandwidth Constraints Model for DS-TE networks", Proceedings of IEEE GLOBECOM 2007.
- [9] F. Le Faucheur (b), "Protocol Extensions for Support of DiffServ-aware MPLS Traffic Engineering", IETF, RFC 4124, June 2005.
- [10] M. Macdougall, "Simulating Computer Systems Techniques and Tools", The Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press. 1987.